

**QISHLOQ XO'JALIGI MAHSULOTLARINI YETISHTIRISHDA
ZARURIY SUVNI TARATISHDA SUV TEJAMKOR QURILMALAR VA
TEXNOLOGIYALAR TO'G'RISIDA MULOHAZALAR.**

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Annotatsiya: *ushbu maqolada hozirgi kundagi suv tanqisligi muammolari va muammolarning yechimlarini topish uchun fikr -mulohazalar keltirilgan. G'o'za qatorlarini oralariga suv taratishda g'o'za tupi uchun me'yorlar va suv sarfining ushbu me'yorga keltirish uchun takliflar keltirilgan.*

Аннотация: *На этом статье проведена проблема о недостаточности воды и для решение в этой проблема свои соображения. Нормативы для полива между рядами стеблей хлопчатника и проведена рекомендация для достижения расход воды этой нормы.*

Abstract: *This article discusses the problem of water shortage and provides its own considerations for solving this problem. Standards for irrigation between rows of cotton stems and recommendations for achieving water consumption of this norm have been made.*

Kalit so'zlar: *suv, sug'orish, qator, oraligi, g'o'za, tup, me'yor, suv sarfi, maydon, mahsulot.*

Ключевой слово: *вода, полив, ряд, между, хлопок, стеблей, норма, расход, площадь, продукта.*

Keyword: *water, watering, row, between, cotton, stems, rate, consumption, area, product.*

Bizga ma'lumkm Markaziy Osiyoning qirg'oqchil mintaqasida qishloq xo'jaligi mahsulotlarining yetishtirish va ishlab chiqarishni jadallashtiruvchi asosiy yo'nalishlardan biri bo'lib sug'oriladigan dehqonchilik hisoblanadi.

O'zbekiston Respublikasining umumiy maydoni 447,4 ming km² bo'lib, shundan 22614 ming gektarini qishloq xo'jaligi ekinlari ekiladigan maydon tashkil etadi. 20 asr davomida sug'oriladigan maydoni 2,36 marotabaga ko'paydi ya'ni 1809,5ming gektardan 4276,1ming gektarga yetkazildi. Respublikada lalmikor dehqonchilik maydoni 743ming gektarni tashkil etadi. O'zbekiston respublikasida yetishtirilayotgan qishloq xo'jaligi mahsulotlarining asosiy qismini ya'ni 97% ni sug'oriladigan yerlardan olinmoqda.

Ushbu yerlarni sug'orish uchun suvning muvozonati (balansi):

Yog'ingarchilik, km³/yil- 74,1

Mahalliy suv oqimi, km³/yil-9,5

Bug'lanish, km³/yil-64,6

Mahalliy suv resurslari: km³/yil-9,5

1km².ga ming m³/yil-21,2

Transchegaraviy ya'ni qo'shni davlatlardan kelib tushuvchi, km³/yil-98,1

Jami suv $9,5+98,1=107,6 \text{ km}^3/\text{yil}$

Hozirgi kunda sir emaski kundun-kunga butun jahonga, shu jumladan O'zbekistonga ham suv tanqisligi sezilarli darajada oshib bormoqda. Bunday suv tanqisligining vujudga kelishiga turli xildagi omillar sabab bo'lmoqda. O'zbekistonda suv tanqisligining oshishiga asosiy sabablardan biri bo'lib transchegaraviy daryolarda suvlarning keskin kamayishi hisoblanadi. O'zbekiston asosan ikkita transchegaraviy daryolar, Amudaryo va Sirdaryodan suv bilan ta'minlanadi. Oxirgi yillarga kelib ushbu daryolarning suvlari keskin darajada kamayib ketishi O'zbekistonda yanada suv tanqisligini oshishiga olib kelmoqda.

Ushbu yuqoridagilarni inobatga olgan hamda O'zbekistonda yetishtiriladigan qishloq xo'jaligi mahsulotlari uchun suv sarfini tejoychi qurilma va texnologiyalarni joriy etish davr talabi bo'lib hisoblanadi. Aynan ushbu muammoni yechimini topish va suv tanqisligining qishloq xo'jaligi mahsulotlarning yetishtirishda ta'sirini kamaytirish va oldini olish maqsadida davlatimiz rahbariyati tomonidan bir qancha qarorlar va farmonlar chiqarilgan: O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining "2018-2019 yillarda irrigatsiyani rivojlantirish va sug'oriladigan yerlarning meliorativ holatini yaxshilash davlat dasturi to'g'risida"gi PQ-3405-sonli 2017 yil 27 noyabrdagi qarori, O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining "Paxta xom ashyosini yetishtirishda tomchilatib sug'orish texnologiyalaridan keng foydalanish uchun qulay shart-sharoitlar yaratishga oid kechiktirib bo'lmaydigan chora-tadbirlar to'g'risida"gi PQ-4087-sonli 2018yil 27 dekabrdagi qarori, O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining "Suv resurslarini boshqarish tizimini yanada takomillashtirish chora-tadbirlari to'g'risida"gi PQ-4486-sonli 2019 yil 9 oktyabrdagi qarori, O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining "Qishloq xo'jaligida yer va suv resurslaridan samarali foydalanish chora-tadbirlari to'g'risida"gi PF-5742-sonli 17 iyundagi farmonlari shular jumlasiga kiradi. Ushbu qarorlar va farmonlarni ijrosini ta'minlash maqsadida mamlakatimiz olimlari tomonidan bir qator suv tejamkor qurilmalar va texnologiyalar yaratilib, ishlab chiqarishga tadbir etilmoqda. Ayrimlari esa eksperiment-sinov tajribasidan o'tkazilib, yaxshi ko'rsatgichlar olinmoqda va bu ko'rsatgichlar ishlab chiqarishga tavsiya etilib kelinmoqda. Bunday qurilmalar qatoriga yer ostidan tomchilatib sug'orish qurilmasi hisoblanadi. Ushbu qurilma bir necha yildan buyon Buxoro tabiiy resurslarni boshqarish institutining tajriba uchastqasidan sinovdan o'tkazilib kelinmoqda. Olingan tajriba natijalari ijobiy bo'lib, hozirgi kunda Madaniyat Muxammad Iffat fermer xo'jaligida tadbir etilmoqda.

Xuddu shunday qurilmalardan biri bo'lib "Harakatlanib g'o'za qator oralariga suv taratish suv tejamkor qurilma va texnologiyasi" hisoblanadi. Ushbu qurilmaning xomaki sinovlari o'tkazilib, ijobiy natijalar olinmoqda. Endi bu qurilmaning ishlab chiqarish varianti tayyorlanmoqda va institutning tajriba uchastkasida hamda fermer xo'jaliklarda ishlab chiqarish tajribasini o'tkazish uchun tayyorlanmoqda. Bu qurilmaning boshqa suv tejamkor qurilmalardan asosiy farqi shundaki, u g'o'za qator oralarida suv taratishda, suvni faqat g'o'za

tubining ostiga ya'ni uning ildizi atrofiga uzatadi. Quyida g'oz qator oralarida suv taratishda suvning uzatish sxemasi keltirilgan.

1-rasm. G'oz qator oralariga suv taratish uchun suv tejamkor qurilmaning sxemasi.
 1-suv manbai; 2-boshqarish pulti; 3-suv nasosi; 4-suv o'tkazgich quvuri; 5-vertikal suv quvuri; 6-burchak ostida joylashgan suv quvuri; 7-quvurlar orasidagi burchakni sozlagich; 8- gorizontal suv quvurlari; 9-quvurning suv uzatuvchi oxirgi uchi(nakonechnik). α =suv quvurlari orasidagi burchak

2-rasm. G'oz qator oralarida suv taratilishining ko'ndalang kesimidagi ko'rinishi.
 1-quvurning suv taratuvchi oxirigi uchi (nakonechnik); 2-jo'yakning ikkinchi devori; 3-g'ozaning poyasi (tubi); 4-suv quyiladigan jo'yak.

Yuqoridagi sxemalardan ko'rinib turibiki, g'oz qatorlari oralarida ushbu uslub suv taratilganda, suv asosan g'ozaning ildiziga tomon yo'naltirilgan bo'lib, qolgan joylariga esa deyarli suv uzatilmaydi. Aynan shuning hisobidan boshqa suv tejamkor qurilmalarga nisbatan ushbu qurilmaning suv tejamkorligini 2-3 martaga oshishiga erishiladi. Ilmiy izlanishlar manbalari taxlil qilinganda bir gektar paxta maydonida har bir vegetatsiya davriga sug'orish uchun suvning sarfi ananaviy sug'orishda 10-13 ming m^3 tashkil etarkan. Me'yoriy suvning sarfi esa har vegetatsiya davrida 3-5 ming m^3 deb, me'yoriy xujjatlarda keltirilgan.

Manbalardan bizga ma'lumki bir tup g'oz ko'chati uchun suvning sarfi,

g'ozaning massasiga qaraganda 200 marta katta bo'lishi mumkin ekan. Demak, bir tup g'ozaning o'rtacha massasi 0,5-1,0 kg bo'lsa, unda bir tup g'oz uchun bir yillik vegetatsiya davrida 100-200 kg.gacha ($0,1-0,2 \text{ m}^3$) suv sarflashi kerak. Agar bir gektar ekin maydoniga o'rtacha 80-120 ming tup g'oz bo'lsa, unda bir gektar paxta maydoniga bir yillik vegetatsiya davridagi suvning sarfi o'rtacha 8-12 ming m^3 ni tashkil etishi kerak. Paxta (g'oz) ko'chatining vegetatsiya davrida yerning holatidan bog'liq holda 4-6 martacha sug'oradi. Demak ananaviy usulda paxtalarini sug'organda bir yillik vegetatsiya davrida 40-80 ming m^3 .gacha suv sarflanar ekan. Me'yoriy suvning sarfi esa 12-30 ming m^3 .gacha bo'lishi kerak. Bundan shunday xulosa qilish kerakki, g'oz ko'chatlari uchun suvning sarfini imkon qadar me'yoriy ko'rsatgichgacha keltirish kerak.

Yuqoridagilardan kelib chiqib, hozirgi kundagi suvning tanqisligi davrida bizlar taklif qilayotgan qurilmamiz qisman suv sarfining me'yoriy ko'rsatgichlariga olib kelish xizmat qiladi.

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